

Network Digital Twins Data Connectors Using International Data Spaces

Allen Abishek¹, Lluís Gifre Renom¹, Ricard Vilalta¹, Raul Muñoz¹, Xavier Masip-Bruin², Adrian Asensio²

¹*Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya - CERCA (CTTC-CERCA)*

²*Advanced Network Architectures Lab (CRAAX), Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)*

aabishek@cttc.es

Abstract— Network Digital Twins (NDTs) are gaining significant importance within the domain of Autonomous Network Operations. Critical processes, including continuous monitoring, predictive maintenance, and "what-if" scenario testing, require reliable and secure communication between the physical network and its digital counterpart to ensure accurate replication.

This paper proposes a novel architectural framework designed to facilitate secure and robust communication between a real physical network and its NDT.

Index Terms—International Data Space, TRUE Connector, SDN controller, ADRENALINE Testbed, Interoperability.

I. INTRODUCTION

Network Digital Twins (NDTs) serve as dynamic, real-time digital counterparts to physical network infrastructures. These virtual replicas have emerged as indispensable tools for automating network operations, offering a real-time, virtualized environment that enables comprehensive monitoring, sophisticated simulation, proactive optimization, and informed decision-making [1].

By continuously maintaining an accurate and up-to-date model of the network's topology, its current operational state, and its performance metrics, NDTs significantly enhance situational awareness for network operators and provide a robust foundation for the development and deployment of intelligent management systems. The ability to safely test and validate proposed network changes through predictive simulations within the NDT environment minimizes the potential for service disruptions and strongly supports continuous integration and delivery practices in network operations. Furthermore, NDTs are central to the implementation of closed-loop automation, allowing Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI/ML) agents to simulate, evaluate, and dynamically apply optimized decisions with minimal human intervention [2]. The reliance on real-time data and automated decision-making processes within NDTs underscores a critical requirement for secure and dependable data exchange. [3].

The deployment of NDTs often leverages cloud infrastructure to achieve more efficient life-cycle management, capitalizing on the dynamic allocation of computing resources to optimize both performance and scalability. While cloud deployment offers significant advantages in terms of resource elasticity, it also introduces new security considerations and potential vulnerabilities associated with distributed environ-

ments. This need for secured communication further complicates the challenge of ensuring robust data security and maintaining data sovereignty across a distributed ecosystem.

This paper addresses the critical need for secure communication in such environments by presenting a novel architecture designed to facilitate secure interactions between an NDT and its corresponding physical network. A key enabling factor for this secure communication framework is the integration of International Data Spaces (IDS), which provides a well-established framework for sovereign data sharing [4]. IDS offers a comprehensive framework designed to enable the sovereign and self-determined exchange of data between organizations. This framework plays a crucial role in supporting the development of future business models and fostering growth within the digital economy. At its core, IDS aims to establish a network of trusted data, guided by the fundamental principle of digital sovereignty. The core principles of data sovereignty inherent in the IDS framework can be directly applied to the vast amounts of data generated and utilized by NDTs. Network operators can leverage IDS to maintain granular control over the usage policies governing their network data, even when this data is shared with the NDT platform or with other authorized entities within the network management ecosystem.

The authors Lantz et al in the paper [5] demonstrate how a network emulator in conjunction with an Software Defined Networking (SDN) controller can behave as a network digital twin for an optical transport network. The real network behaviour is replicated in a network emulator which is Mininet-Optical. And network operations done on the actual network are replicated on its NDT with the help of a SDN controller which sends state information of the actual network to the NDT in a continual and automated fashion. This paper is interested in communication between the real network, which is an optical transport network and its virtual twin counterpart running on mininet-optical.

The paper Kalogeropoulos et al. [6] introduce the concept of Edge Data Space (EdgeDS), a novel architectural framework that integrates the principles of the International Data Spaces (IDS) with Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) to facilitate secure and interoperable data exchange among diverse stakeholders within and beyond the MEC environment. The proposed approach enables the dynamic instantiation of IDS Connectors, offered as a 'IDS-as-a-Service' to establish

Fig. 1. Architecture of Secure Communication using IDS.

secure communication pathways between MEC applications and other applications residing across MEC nodes and the broader Telco-cloud infrastructure. The paper also provides a comprehensive discussion on the lifecycle management of IDS Connectors, detailing processes such as composition, instantiation, deployment, and operational management in coordination with MEC applications. Furthermore, the authors explore practical use cases, particularly emphasizing the potential of this architecture to support autonomous driving systems by enabling more responsive and efficient vehicular communication and transportation systems. This paper plans to build upon the previous work and create an architectural design for secure communication between NDT and its physical network counterpart as discussed in section I.

NDTs and their physical network counterparts are required to interface with each other in a continual, bi-directional fashion. The deployment of the NDT on a cloud infrastructure can facilitate more efficient life-cycle management, leveraging the dynamic allocation of compute resources to optimize performance and scalability [7]. This paper sees an opportunity to contribute a novel architecture for secure communications between an NDT and the physical network counterpart.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The architecture proposed in this paper is depicted in Fig. 2. The real network is assumed to be a topology of network elements of an optical network such as ROADMs, Optical Amplifiers, Optical Fibers, and Optical Network Terminals. These network elements are controlled by a logically centralized SDN controller that communicates to its virtual counterpart through the Application Programming Interface (API) gateway of the NDT, which might be a Representational State Transfer (REST) server.

An IDS Gateway is a data connector component that acts as a 'gateway' to access the IDS. In order to create a minimum viable IDS, a minimum of two IDS Gateway instances are required. Each entity is connected and coupled

to one IDS Gateway instance. The entity posts information as objects into the IDS Gateway instance using the API endpoints with appropriate security authentication credentials. Upon verification of credentials by the IDS Gateway instance, the information/object is posted. Once information resides in an IDS Gateway it can be accessed by other entities which are part of the IDS and other IDS Gateway instances. In the system architecture of this paper, the entities of interest are the SDN controller of the real physical network and the API server of the NDT and each are connected to an instance of the IDS Gateway. It is assumed that these IDS Gateway are already instantiated, operational, and linked through secure communication protocols. Examples of such protocols that are supported by IDS Gateway include HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS) which is HTTP with Transport Layer Security (TLS), WebSockets secured using WebSocket Secure (WSS), and the IDS Communication Protocol version 2 (IDSCPv2) [8].

Figure 2 outlines the data exchange workflow between two IDS Gateways. In this model, the SDN controller of the real physical network transmits a data object to its corresponding IDS Gateway, which securely forwards the object through the Data Space until it reaches the target IDS Gateway. The receiving connector stores the object in its local database. The receiving IDS Gateway is coupled to the API of the NDT of the physical real network, the NDT retrieves the object in its Connector instance using an HTTP GET request. This process of the workflow ensures the flow of information from the real network to the NDT over a secure connectivity entity, which is the IDS, the IDS guarantees secure communication over public networks like the internet reducing capital expenditure requirements of private networks to ensure secure connectivity between entities. The communication process is inherently bidirectional as IDS Gateways part of the IDS can interface with each other, allowing continuous and secure information flow between multiple geographically distributed systems using the International Data Space (IDS) framework [4].

Fig. 2. Workflow of communication between NDT and Real Physical Network.

III. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

For this implementation, the IDS Gateway used is the open-source TRUE Connector. Within this system, the IDS Gateway that is coupled to the NDT and which receives data from the SDN controller of the real physical network acts as the 'consumer' gateway, while the other IDS Gateway that forwards data from the physical network to the consumer IDS Gateway is considered as the 'provider'. The deployed SDN controller is ETSI TeraFlowSDN (TFS) and NDT uses mininet-optical as described in [7].

This section presents the validation and performance results of the NDT-Connector architecture as illustrated in Fig. 2. For this paper's validation, two Ubuntu servers are each configured with an instance of the TRUE Connector IDS Gateway, interconnected over an IP-based Ethernet network to emulate two entities communicating through the IDS that are spatially separated. The validation process is divided into three sequential phases: a) in the first phase, a connectivity service is posted by the SDN Controller of the real physical network into the 'provider' IDS Gateway instance as a JSON object; b) in the second phase, the service is transmitted to the 'consumer' IDS Gateway instance on the second Ubuntu server; and in c) the third phase, the API gateway of the NDT gets the object/connectivity service from the 'consumer' IDS Gateway instance. This experiment uses HTTP with basic authentication (username and password) for inter-connector communication to simplify the implementation process. In order to put or pull information as JSON objects into the IDS Gateway, the contract negotiation process in the IDS Gateway instance must be initiated. The credentials (basic authentication username and password for HTTP, Secure Socket Layer (SSL) for HTTPS, SSL certificate for IDSCPv2 and WSS, must be validated by the IDS Gateway instance) are verified and upon successful verification, the entity connecting to the IDS can communicate with other IDS Gateway instances within the IDS. However, for large-scale industrial deployments, more advanced and secure communication protocols like WSS, and IDSCPv2 are highly recommended. Each IDS Gateway instance is deployed as a set of docker containers that are part of a container network, bound to a network port on its respective host server.

The validation executes all three phases across 25 iterations, with timing data from each phase collected and used to construct the CDF distribution to evaluate its performance characteristics.

Figure 3 presents the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of the time taken to POST the connectivity service as a JSON object by the SDN controller of the real network into the 'provider' IDS instance via its HTTP API endpoint provided by TRUE Connector.

Fig. 3. Time taken to POST connectivity service to Consumer Connector Instance

The mean time to post the connectivity service into the provider IDS Gateway instance is 0.76 seconds with a median time of 0.74 seconds. The next step in the validation is to calculate the CDF distribution of the time taken to post the information from the 'provider' IDS Gateway instance into the 'consumer' connector instance. The results of this validation are seen in Fig. 4.

The mean time taken to pull the connectivity service from the provider IDS Gateway instance is seen to be 0.87 seconds, while the median time is 0.9 seconds. The time taken is slightly higher because of the time taken by data to travel physically from one server running the 'provider' IDS Gateway instance to the server running the 'consumer' IDS Gateway instance. The mean time taken to transmit data from consumer to provider is expected to increase as the distance between them

Fig. 4. Time taken to POST connectivity service from Provider Connector instance to Consumer Connector Instance

increases, and also the nature of the network connecting the servers also affects the time taken as IP Ethernet networks are slower compared to optical transport networks where information is carried by light.

The latency in time taken to POST and GET resources to and from the IDS Gateways can be attributed to factors like bandwidth available at the Transport Network, the communication overhead due to the size of the data payload that is sent in IP packets, and the security overhead based on encryption mechanisms if they are present.

The final result of validation is to graph the CDF distribution of the time taken by the SDN controller to pull (via a GET request) information from the 'consumer' IDS Gateway instance. This can be seen in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Time taken to GET connectivity service from connector Connector instance

The mean time taken to get the connectivity service object posted in the 'consumer' IDS Gateway instance is 0.56 seconds, and the median time is 0.56 seconds. This low deviation of median from mean displays an almost perfect Gaussian distribution. Further enhancements in security can be done by encrypting the data before posting it into the IDS Gateway to ensure safer transmission of data; this would ensure that an entity with access to IDS the connector to retrieve information

will not be able to decipher the payload unless it has the key to decrypt the data that was sent in the payload, thus adding an extra layer of security.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper has introduced a secure method for information exchange between a physical network and its virtual counterpart, where both components are administratively separated. Future development will focus on validating the safety and robustness of the IDS framework by simulating potential security threats. This includes executing targeted attacks on IDS Gateway, such as a Distributed Denial of Service Attacks (DDoS) to disrupt availability and sever connectivity between entities, or Man-in-the-Middle attacks to compromise data integrity during transmission and develop countermeasures.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The research leading to this publication has been partially financed by the Horizon Europe COBALT Project (101119602) and by Ministerio de Asuntos Económicos y Transformación Digital and the European Union-Next GenerationEU in the frameworks of the Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia and of the Mecanismo de Recuperación y Resiliencia trough UNICO-5G I+D 6GMICROSDN project under references TSI-063000-2021-19, TSI-063000-2021-20, TSI-063000-2021-21 MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/FEDER/UE and by the RELAMPAGO project (Grant PID2021-127916OB-I00), funded by MICIU/AEI/ 10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF/EU.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. X. Nguyen, R. Trestian, D. To, and M. Tatipamula, "Digital twin for 5g and beyond," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 59, no. 2, pp. 10–15, 2021.
- [2] ETSI, "Zero-touch network and Service Management (ZSM); Network Digital Twin," ETSI, Tech. Rep. ETSI GR ZSM 015 V1.1.1, February 2024.
- [3] Y. Yigit, B. Bal, A. Karameseoglu, T. Q. Duong, and B. Canberk, "Digital twin-enabled intelligent ddos detection mechanism for autonomous core networks," *IEEE Communications Standards Magazine*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 38–44, 2022.
- [4] B. Otto, J. Juerjens, and S. L. et al., "Design principles for data spaces," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Big Data*, 2019, pp. 4472–4481.
- [5] B. Lantz, A. A. Díaz-Montiel, J. Yu, C. Rios, M. Ruffini, and D. Kilper, "Demonstration of software-defined packet-optical network emulation with mininet-optical and onos," in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference*. Optica Publishing Group, 2020, pp. M3Z–9.
- [6] I. Kalogeropoulos *et al.*, "Edgeds: Data spaces enabled multi-access edge computing," in *EuCNC/6G Summit*. IEEE, 2023.
- [7] R. Vilalta, L. Gifre, R. Casellas, R. Muñoz, R. Martínez, A. Mozo, A. Pastor, D. López, and J. P. Fernández-Palacios, "Applying digital twins to optical networks with cloud-native sdn controllers," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 61, no. 12, pp. 128–134, 2023.
- [8] F. Institute, "Ids communication protocol v2 documentation," <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-Communication-Protocol>, 2021.